

Nordic Seas Data Management Plan

Version 0.1

EMSO ERIC
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History of changes

Version	Date	Change	Author(s)
0.1	03/01/2024	First version	Rocío Castaño Primo

DMP Nordic Seas

Dataset Overview	
Dataset Title	Timeseries observations from EMSO sites in the Nordic Seas
Dataset Description	<p>Hydrographic, currents and biogeochemical time-series datasets from five fixed stations: Svinøy, Station M, Fram Strait, South Cape, Mohn observatory; located across the Nordic Seas (78.8 – 62.8 °N, -2 – 16 °E). The time coverage varies from >20 years from some long-term monitoring stations to sites being newly deployed during the participation in EMSO ERIC. The depth of observations range from 50 to 3000 m below sea surface.</p> <p>While all sites collect data from fixed stations, they are rather heterogeneous in their particular configurations, set of sensors and data flow prior to distribution via ERDDAP. Svinøy consists of two subsurface moorings close together (north and south) equipped with current meters at three depths. Station M and Fram Strait are single moorings with a variety of physical and biogeochemical sensors. South Cape and Mohn observatory consist of a bottom unit and a subsurface mooring.</p>

Data Collection
<p>Data from the five sites in the Nordic Seas EMSO node are collected by arrays of sensors deployed in the mooring lines and bottom landers. All sites collect subsurface observations and to the date of this DMP none of them has NRT capabilities. The sites are generally serviced, and the data collected once a year, barring exceptional circumstances. Some stations may show short temporal gaps in their time series due to the sensors needing to be serviced and lack of replacement sensors.</p> <p>The variables measured vary by site:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Svinøy: pressure, temperature, salinity and ocean currents - Station M: pressure, temperature, salinity, partial pressure of CO₂ (pCO₂) - Fram Strait: pressure, temperature, salinity, currents, dissolved oxygen, pH, pCO₂ - South Cape: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Bottom unit: pressure, temperature, salinity, currents, methane, pCO₂, pH, dissolved oxygen o Subsurface mooring: pressure, temperature, salinity, currents, methane - Mohn observatory: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Bottom unit: pressure, temperature, salinity, turbidity o Subsurface mooring: pressure, temperature, salinity, currents, turbidity <p>Data format: UNIDATA NetCDF (data comply with the NetCDF EMSO profile). Data metadata: ISO 19115, ISO 19139, Climate and Forecast (CF), Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (ACDD) metadata conventions.</p> <p>Services: ERDDAP</p>

Data and metadata quality control (QC) procedures, including sensor calibration, are mandatory and based on open standard practices when available. QC is a requirement for data release and the responsibility of the principal investigator or owner of the system, instrument or sample collector that acquired the observations and submits the data for further distribution.

Documentation and Metadata

The metadata are standardized into NetCDF files, following the format conventions and standards by OceanSites and EMSO ERIC.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

EMSO Nordic Seas data is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)

Storage and Backup

All data are secured on long-term archiving systems (Norwegian Marine Data Center <http://metadata.nmdc.no/UserInterface/#/>, Norwegian Polar Data Center <https://data.npolar.no/dataset> and UiT's Dataverse repository <https://dataverse.no/dataverse/uit>). Data are stored in an open and self-descriptive format.

While under work (calibration, QC, initial formatting and documentation), data are stored and backed up following the guidelines of the respective responsible institutions (see "Responsibilities and resources").

Selection and Preservation

All QCed datasets are long term preserved in long-term archives (see "Storage and backup").

Data Sharing

Datasets are available via IMR's ERDDAP server (search term: NorEMSO): <https://erddap.hi.no> and EMSO ERDDAP. Alternatively, data can be downloaded from their respective long-term data archives.

Responsibilities and Resources

The data incoming from the different sites are the responsibility of their respective institutions:

- Svinøy: Institute of Marine Research (Norway)
- Station M: NORCE Research
- Fram Strait: Norwegian Polar Institute
- South Cape: University of Tromsø

- Mohn observatory: University of Bergen

The Data Management team of the NorEMSO project is responsible for the further distribution of data to EMSO ERIC systems and the additional reformatting and documenting that may be required.

